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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13341785>**LITERARY TEXTS IN THE ACQUISITION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN HIGHER SCHOOLS****Abstract.**

Reading literary texts is very important in foreign language teaching. The units used here form a special specific layer of the lexicon, perform different functions in speech and have a different structure and a separate semantic integrity. The search for precise criteria for reading different types of literary texts has always been a complex problem, and as a result phraseological criteria such as repetition, stability, semantic uniqueness and others, known as fiction, have emerged. This article focuses on the application of English language learning opportunities of students studying in higher schools through literary texts. During the research, the conditions for students to read literary texts with methods that will serve the easy acquisition of a foreign language are explained. The presented article explains the rules followed in reading classes, shows ways to overcome difficulties in understanding the text through various artistic works, and highlights the importance of "home reading" classes in developing students' reading habits. Developing reading habits in English through literary works makes students interested in reading, improves their reading speed, and ultimately increases their enthusiasm for learning English.

Keywords: English language, literary text, high education, teaching, methods

Introduction. The formation of skills and habits of reading literary texts in English is considered one of the important factors in all stages of the process of learning foreign languages. At the initial stage, the formation of students' reading technique in a foreign language is envisaged. In reading lessons, students' speech develops and their vocabulary is enriched. Therefore, when the text is easy, exercises reflecting speaking skills and questions related to the text are given.

Discussion. If the text is difficult in terms of content, then the approach changes, and in this case, along with acquiring new information, it is necessary to improve foreign language skills. It is advisable to observe the following rules in reading lessons:

The artistic text should not be too large in volume;

In reading lessons, texts should be chosen in which the number of unknown words is small and the student understands the content of the text without a dictionary;

Literary texts should be chosen according to the specialty;

The fiction text should not be boring and uninteresting. The text should be taken from modern literature, it should cover topics related to youth, family, sports, friendship, etc., which arouse students' interest, artistic pieces should be selected that interest students; (Mustafa, 2021, 34)

New words in the literary text must be explained;

Students must understand the content of the material they read;

Work should be done on studies for the development of reading technique;

Technical means should be used for expressive reading (Teaching reading skills in foreign language, 1996, 54).

In reading lessons, vocabulary should be explained before moving on to the text, and students should pay attention to the correct pronunciation of words after they are introduced to new words. However, sometimes there are words whose meaning is clear from the content of the text or the sentence in which it is used. Such words are not explained in the reading process, and translating new words into English

makes it possible to achieve a direct goal and takes less time. But I think that when the teacher teaches new words visually, either by showing the object itself or a picture, the words are better remembered. Visually taught new words should be explained before reading, because showing the object itself, a model or a picture during the reading process causes the students' attention to be completely distracted from the reading text.

Here, it is possible to overcome difficulties in understanding the text with various tasks without resorting to translation.

1. Explaining new words to students before moving on to the text.

2. The teacher should use synonyms in explaining new words. As he writes the new words on the board, he can also write their synonyms in front of them.

Antonyms are also used to explain new words. The teacher writes its antonym in front of familiar words, and this, in turn, leads to the elimination of difficulties.

In the lesson, students can be divided into groups and new words can be taught effectively in the form of a competition. For example: to choose the verbs corresponding to the blank places in the text or to construct sentences from the given new words.

Word associations. For this purpose, the key words related to the topic are written on the board. The students are instructed to say or write in their notebooks the associations that word creates in them (other words that come to mind when they hear or see this word). The words that the students say or write down in their notebooks about the key word on the topic are written on the board in a few minutes. By connecting and summarizing these words, an idea is formed about the main goals of the new topic. Based on that idea, the study of new material is started. Word associations can be applied at the beginning, at the end of the lesson, orally and in writing. The application of word associations at the beginning of the study of the topic aims to determine the knowledge of students about this issue. At the end of the lesson, through word associations, students reveal the new knowledge they have already mastered.

In order for students to enrich their vocabulary and better master the words used in the content of the text, it may be suggested to add a prefix or suffix to the given words.

One of the main directions of work on the text is teaching its content. Working on content is an important tool to help students reinforce their newly acquired vocabulary. When working on the content of the text, first of all, it is necessary to recall the facts remembered by the students during reading and to work on the questions related to the text. Questions should cover the content of the text. At this time, students can read the text, ask each other questions, think, search and find answers to the given questions. This allows you to check the level of their skills and habits of making appropriate sentences. At the same time, students' speech habits and logical thinking are developed. During the question-and-answer process, the questions are gradually made more complex for the students to think more, so that the students can speak English better.

Many students find it difficult to narrate the text. In this case, they are instructed to divide the text into several parts and give a title to each part. In this way, students understand the text to its smallest detail. In order to develop dialogue and monologue speaking skills, students are given the task of writing a short ending to the text using new vocabulary in pairs.

Preparation of a project related to the read text can be individual or group. Speaking with their own projects, students develop monologue speech habits, present the project for discussion and succeed in establishing a dialogue.

In reading lessons, the teacher should be able to reveal the creative abilities of the students. Homework, which is one of the important ways of creative application of knowledge and skills acquired in classes, requires a new approach. Unlike traditional lessons, in an active/interactive lesson it is not correct to make checking homework the goal. In order not to waste time, the teacher can find out the level of execution (acceptance) of the tasks in a selective way by organizing an interview, presentation, discussion, etc. in a short time. He can independently determine the content and form of homework based on the learning objectives (Developing Reading Skills, 1994, 19).

Work on deformed text. In this type of writing, the place of the sentences in the text is changed. Students create a text by reconstructing the sentences given in the order. In doing this type of writing, students acquire the habit of constructing sentences and the ability to express their ideas in a certain sequence.

Read with breaks. The text of the work is divided into parts in advance. After a part is read, there is a pause and the teacher asks questions about the content of the read part. Answers are heard and the next part is read. The third and fourth parts are also read in this way, and an interview on the content is conducted during breaks.

Predicted reading. In the lesson devoted to the study of the content of artistic works, a break is made after reading a part of the work. Students say their guesses about the further development of events and

record them in the table. In the table, they also note what they based their probabilities on. After reading a new passage, they go back to their previous assumptions and clarify to what extent it resonates with the events that happened. This rule continues until the end (Bailey, 2015).

Each reader has certain expectations at the moment of first acquaintance with the material to be read, and in the process of reading, these expectations are either confirmed, denied, or similar. At the same time, the reader has to take a critical look at the writing, re-analyze the writer's thoughts and draw independent conclusions, which leads to the development of his reading habits.

In groups where a foreign language is taught, "home reading" lessons are held to develop students' reading habits. "Home reading" classes have an exceptional importance not only in developing reading habits, but also in language learning (Developing Reading Skills, 1994, 63).

If during reading, students have to find answers to the questions asked by the teacher about the material, in "home reading" lessons, the student who "assigns" the reading has to answer the questions asked by the audience. However, sometimes the teacher can change the form of the question-and-answer process in order to clarify how the students understood the material they listened to, that is, the student narrating the work asks questions about certain parts of the work and determines whether the students understand those parts. This also helps to form students to be more responsible during the lesson, and after all this, the teacher can fully discuss the read material. At this time, it becomes clear at what level the student who reads the work has understood the material.

As a result, it can be concluded that both "home reading" and "reading" classes have the same goal, that is, to develop reading habits that have a direct role in students' language acquisition. It is very important to use the above linguistic didactic tasks in reading lessons. In this process, the vocabulary of students increases, they not only learn the content of the text, but also remember the structure of word combinations and expressions, enrich their memory and develop the habit of making correct sentences. Students' reading speed increases, reading habits are developed and strengthened. Reading lessons arouse students' interest in reading and increase their desire to learn this language.

Every reader has certain expectations at the moment of the first acquaintance with the literary material to be read, and in the process of reading these expectations are either confirmed, denied, or similar. At the same time, the reader has to take a critical look at the writing, re-analyze the writer's thoughts and draw independent conclusions, which leads to the development of his reading habits. In groups where a foreign language is taught, "home reading" lessons are held to develop students' reading habits. "Home reading" classes have an exceptional importance not only in developing reading habits, but also in language learning (Developing Reading Skills, 1994, 63).

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